

ART CATALOGUE
Ataba Opeyemi John

Profile

Ataba Opeyemi – Artist, Educator, and Art Director

Ataba Opeyemi is a seasoned Nigerian visual artist and art educator with over 12 years of experience in fine arts, design, and arts education. He currently serves as the Arts Education Officer at **Oasis Royal Academy** in Osogbo, where he designs curriculum, coordinates programs, and fosters artistic development in students of diverse age groups.

He holds a **Master of Arts in Art Education** and a **Bachelor's degree in Fine and Applied Arts Education** from **Obafemi Awolowo University**. Opeyemi's career spans roles as an art director, fine arts instructor, and NGO program coordinator, combining creative leadership with strategic planning and community engagement.

As a member of multiple professional networks—including the **Nigeria Society for Arts Education** and the **Civil Coalition on Education for All**—he advocates for quality education and cultural preservation. He is also a published academic with works focusing on Yoruba art, education reform, and cross - cultural heritage.

Title: *Thunderous Gallop*
Medium: Mixed Media on Canvas
Size: 6X4
Year: 2024

Title: *The Drummer*

Medium: Mixed Media on
Canvas

Size: 6X10

Year: 2009

Title: *The Drummer*

Medium: Mixed Media on
Canvas

Size: 6X10

Year: 2010

Title: River Side

Medium: Mixed Media on
Canvas

Size: 6X10

Year: 2024

Title: Face off

Medium: OIL COLOUR on
Canvas

Size: 5X12

Year: 2024

Title: Lock up face

Medium: Print Making

Size: 4X6

Year: 2024

Title: The 1000miles
Medium: Pastel and scratching
on a woodboard (wood block)
Size: 6X10
Year: 2024

Title: The Agony of Human
Medium: Printmaking on a
woodboard (wood block)
Size: 6X10
Year: 2023

Title: Who's Next

Medium: Oil colour on Canvas

Size: 6X10

Year: 2023

Title: LAGOS 20s

Medium: Oil colour on
Canvas

Size: 12X8

Year: 2023

Title: The Bride

Medium: Wood block

Printmaking

Size: 16X8

Year: 2023

Title: Birth and Rise
Medium: Acrylic Painting
Size: 16X8
Year: 2024

Title: Target

Medium: Acrylic Painting

Size: 8X10

Year: 2024

Title: Desert Camel
Medium: Oil Painting
Size: 4X12
Year: 2024

Title: Kaba
Medium: Oil Painting
Size: 4X12
Year: 2024

Title: Suplux Love
Medium: Oil Painting
instillation
Size: 10X8
Year: 2024

Title: Focus

Medium: Oil Painting

Impasto

Size: 4X10

Year: 2024

Title: Soar hair

Medium: palette Painting

Impasto

Size: 4X10

Year: 2024

Title: Womanhood
Medium: palette Painting
Impasto
Size: 8X10
Year: 2025

Title: Floodgate

Medium: palette Painting

Size: 10X8

Year: 2025

Title: Newbie

Medium: Wood block
Printmaking

Size: 8X10

Year: 2025

Title: Never Give Up
Medium: Photography
Size: 6X10
Year: 2025

Title: Durban
Medium: Oil Painting
Size: 8X6
Year: 2025

Title: Watchman
Medium: Oil Painting
Size: 5X8
Year: 2025

Title: Fetch Man
Medium: Metal
Size: 4X12
Year: 2024

Title: Hawker
Medium: Metal
Size: 4X12
Year: 2024

Title: Night Guide

Medium: Stone Carving

Size: 3X6

Year: 2020

Title: Shower Night
Medium: Oil Painting
Size: 6X8
Year: 2025

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